

Astro: Temporal Expression Clusters

CGE_dev: Temporal Expression Clusters

ID2: Temporal Expression Clusters

L2-3_CUX2: Temporal Expression Clusters

L4_RORB: Temporal Expression Clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 450

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 606

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 651

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 592

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 826

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 489

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 528

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 336

Cluster 9. Number of genes: 560

Cluster 10. Number of genes: 630

Cluster 11. Number of genes: 834

Cluster 12. Number of genes: 654

L5-6_THEMIS: Temporal Expression Clusters

L5-6_TLE4: Temporal Expression Clusters

LAMP5_NOS1: Temporal Expression Clusters

dev: Temporal Expression Clusters

Micro: Temporal Expression Clusters

Oligo: Temporal Expression Clusters

OPC: Temporal Expression Clusters

PN_dev: Temporal Expression Clusters

PV: Temporal Expression Clusters

PV_SCUBE3: Temporal Expression Clusters

SST: Temporal Expression Clusters

Vas: Temporal Expression Clusters

VIP: Temporal Expression Clusters

